

Social Responsibility and its Relationship to Environmental Sustainable Development

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Abstract

This Study Aime Firstble; To Highlight The Extent Of The Role Played Corporate Social Resposability (SRC). It S Also Aimed To Identify The Most Important Dimension And Characteristics That Characteriz It. Then It Highlight The Most Basic Concepts Of Sustainable Enviromental Developement. Linking CSR To The Most Important Community Enviromental Initiatives, And How To Contribute Sustainable Developement Through The Analytical Discriptive Approach Based On The Discription Of The Phenomenon Of Social Responsibility And Sustainable Enviromental Developement, Through Knowledge Of The Proavtive Studies And The Most Importrant Liturature Associated With The Study. By Analysing Thi Information, the Community Was Reached, Concluding That Social Responsibility Has a Significant Role to Play in Sustainable Enviromental Developement, Which Makes These Companies Competitive for the Distant and the Medieum Debtor.

Keywords: *Social Resposability (SRC), Sustainable Development, Environmental.*

INTRODUCTION

Social responsibility has become a major challenge for economic institutions, which has generated the interest of researchers and international organizations in the concepts of sustainable development, business ethics and governance. Economic institutions have therefore shifted from attention by raising their economic returns to social and environmental concerns that have never been raised before, Having become obliged to find solutions for society and its components and to search for social performance that contributes to the well-being of society and the preservation of the environment, In the light of these environmental variables and the intense competition between economic institutions, economic, political and social changes at the level of business organizations as a result of economic, social and environmental errors and problems have led to a growing interest in social responsibility in business organizations in order to adapt them to their internal and external environment as a result of a response to these changes it has become a necessity and a prerequisite for organizations and sustainable development, and they have to adhere to the principles of social responsibility to strengthen their competitive advantage in order to improve their image and maintain their market viability.

The commitment of the institution to social responsibility activities towards society and the environment is based on a balance between economic prosperity, social well-being and environmental responsibility in order to achieve long-term sustainable development.

Research Problem:

Based on the above, we pose the following problem: where is the contribution of social responsibility to sustainable environmental development? The following sub-problems can also be raised:

- What's social responsibility?
- What does sustainable development mean? And the most important goals it pursues?
- How does social responsibility contribute to sustainable environmental development?

Research main hypothesis:

- ✓ Social responsibility contributes to the consolidation of sustainable environmental development.

Research purposes:

This research paper seeks to identify:

- ❖ The concept of social responsibility and the identification of its most important dimensions and characteristics.
- ❖ To highlight the basic concepts of sustainable environmental development.
- ❖ To identify the extent to which corporate social responsibility can contribute to sustainable environmental development.

Importance of research:

The importance of this research paper is as follows:

- ❖ To inform decision makers of the role of social responsibility in achieving sustainable development.
- ❖ Attempt to integrate social responsibility with sustainable environmental development.
- ❖ The need for companies to adopt social responsibility in achieving sustainable environmental development goals.

Research approach:

We have relied on the analytical descriptive approach in our research, which is defined as the method of studying the current realities of a particular phenomenon through the description of the phenomenon to be studied, as well as on a desk survey of the literature associated with the study. The analysis of the information obtained has been carried out in order to produce general results.

Procedural definitions of the study:

Social responsibility: The social responsibility of business organizations is to take into account meeting and environmental concerns in their management and in managing their relationship with stakeholders. The aim is to satisfy their wishes.

Social responsibility towards the environment: is one of the most important elements of social responsibility as a result of the increase in natural resources and the resulting residues, air pollution, water, soil and irrational exploitation of resources, which leads to environmental problems at all levels.

Sustainable development: sustainable social, economic and environmental development is concerned with making good use of available resources while meeting the needs of individuals and subsequent generations.

Summary of Previous Studies:

- Ahs Kolk, (2016), *The Social Responsibility Of International Business: From Ethics And The Environment To CSR And Sustainable Development*, This Study Addressed Various Social Responsibility (sr) issues during the second half of the twentieth century , so this the most important and essential concept of social responsibility and their relationship with the green environment, responsibilities , poverty , and sustainable development were identified discussed, including key contribution , and promoting the areas to enhance this area.
- Kamal Rostami, Laleh Salhi, *Rural Cooperatives Social Responsibility In Promoting Sustainability Oriented Activities In The Agricultural Sector: Nexus Of Community Enterprise And Government*, This study aimed to provide a growth in which the agriculture sector is defined as well as that the farmers and sustainability -oriented activities, by join corporate social responsibility (CSR) CSR in to the structure of major cooperatives , using the stakeholders theory and the growth of structural equations to bridge the gap with the understanding the relationship between farmers, cooperatives and government .
- Elisabita Venezia, *on the maturity of social responsibility integration in higher education institution: descriptive criteria and conceptual Framework*, the international journal of management education, the result showed that social responsibility (SR) enhances trust among farmers through their participation in cooperatives programmes.
- And also the result showed that increasing the participation sustainable farming and features of social responsibility (SR).
- The study aimed to highlight the importance of social responsibility (SR) and sustainability by integrating elements of SR to achieve sustainable development, by contributing SR to higher education institutions, the study concluded that concrete responsibility in academia polymakers can be achieved, and concluded that we aim to facilitate higher education institutions that embrace education from sustainable development.
- Yubing Yo, Jiawei Xu, Baofeng Huo, Justin, *The Impact Of Supply Chain Social Responsibility Sustainable Performance*, this study aimed ascertain how to achieve sustainable development by dealing with the social and environmental pressures of manufactures that adhere to SR elements based on the stakeholders theory. data was collected from 209 Chinese industrial companies. Structural equation were used. The study concluded that SR in supply chain can improve sustainable performance.
- Seamless SR patterns significantly affect the economy and the environment and help to achieve sustainable performance.
- The study was aimed to integrate elements of SR and green finance into sustainable tourism in Bangladesh in the field of tourism industry that attract domestic and international tourists because of their natural views from variety landscapes and historical sites.

- Also the industry created jobs and increased economic growth to serve poverty, and also to help to achieve sustainable development goals.
- So the study concluded that there is a positive tension between CSR (corporate social responsibility) and the adoption of green finance that helps to create a sustainable tourism industry through the introduction of fiscal and tax concessions for companies that embrace social responsibility (SR) and encourage them more in green finance.

M D.Hasamur Rahman, Tipon Tanchangya, Junaid Rahman, Most. Asikha Aktar, Shanpanchandra Majuunder, Corporate Social Responsibility And Green Financing Behavior In Bangladesh: To Words Sustainable Tourism-this study addressed various issues of social responsibility(SR) during the second half of the twentieth century, identifying the most important concepts of social responsibility (SR), as well as their relationship with the green environment, ethics, responsibilities, poverty and sustainable development, which were discussed, including key contribution and promising areas from promoting and strengthening this area.

One of the most important topics of the modern era is the challenges facing companies, on the one hand, and economic transformations, on the other. This is reflected in their economic and social performance in order to maintain their competitiveness as an open system that is directly influenced and influenced by everything that is happening around them in the business environment, as a result of scientific and technological developments that have taken place, taking into account stakeholders and integrating their social and economic concerns into their overall strategies since their continuation.

The concept of social responsibility takes several definitions as a result of current developments through researchers and international organizations and bodies, all of which feed into a social, economic and environmental framework. Through this chapter, we review in detail the conceptual framework of social responsibility through the following research themes:

☞ **The emergence and evolution of social responsibility:**

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is the concept of attracting global attention and gaining a new resonance in the global economy. The growing interest in corporate social responsibility in recent years has arisen from the emergence of globalization and international trade, which has been reflected in the increasing complexity of new businesses and demands for enhanced transparency and corporate citizenship. The needs of society have exceeded the capacity of Governments to meet them. In this context, the light is increasingly shifting to a focus on the role of business in society and developed firms are seeking to distinguish themselves by sharing corporate social responsibility. (Elasrag, 2015, p 08).

Corporate social responsibility is an ever-evolving idea where businesses are becoming more aware of the persistence of society around them. Corporate social responsibility includes the business company's obligation to society beyond merely maximizing its profits. Corporate social responsibility was not taken seriously and at times was harnessed by commercial companies before the late 1970s, and the change in the CSR approach could be attributed in part to the enactment of new legislation that led to the establishment of several government regulatory bodies during this period of time. The new legislation provided businesses with an additional incentive to allocate appropriate amounts of financial resources to corporate social responsibility rather than to confront harsh government regulations (Jamali & Mirshak, 2007). The attitude towards corporate social responsibility changed significantly in the late 1990s, with corporate social responsibility now becoming a dominant idea promoted by various aspects of society, from companies to governments.

☞ **Concept of social responsibility:**

The concept of corporate social responsibility has become a strategic issue that plays a key and more important role over time, although there is no generally accepted definition, most interpretations is close to the European Commission definition of corporate social responsibility as "firm responsibility for its impact on society." To fulfil its corporate social responsibility, "firms must have a process of integrating social, environmental and ethical concerns, human rights and consumer concerns into their business processes and basic strategy in close collaboration with stakeholders." From this understanding, corporate social responsibility is a cross-cutting model of many regulatory practices aimed at serving stakeholders other than corporate owners, including clients, employees, communities and society as a whole. Although most countries have legally binding regulations that fall within the scope of corporate social responsibility, researchers generally only classify corporate activities voluntarily without legal coercion as corporate social responsibility activities. (Schwoy et al., 2023, p 02) Although there is no clear definition, all competing definitions of corporate social responsibility agree on one thing: society's expectations must be met when planning their own environmental management strategies (Saeidi et al., 2015, p 342).

☞ **Factors influencing the application of social responsibility:**

For the organization's successful adoption of social responsibility, the following considerations must be taken into account (Jomah, 2016, p. 4. 118):

- Legal factors: The law plays a fundamental role in regulating relations between business organizations operating in the same sector and helping to bring about equality between competitors.
- Political factors: The political system plays an important role in the implementation of social responsibility through a system of values and beliefs of government officials.
- Labor market factor: by regulating the organization's relationship with employees through trade unions that protect workers from risks and work towards the provision of new services.
- Capital factor: The focus on obtaining capital for the organizations on the market is well placed through verification of the type of capital available in equity against debt bonds.

☞ **Dimensions of social responsibility:**

Social responsibility is the supposed obligation of actions towards society. Being socially responsible means maximizing positive impacts and minimizing negative impacts on society (clients, owners, employees, society, suppliers, government). There are four types of social responsibility: legal, ethical, economic and charitable. (Nicolae & Sabina, 2010, p 238).Carroll believes that there are dimensions to the measurement and study of social responsibility, which are four integrated and interrelated levels. Therefore, the management of the organization must be made aware of them so that they can develop, grow and survive to achieve the various objectives:

- Economic responsibility.
- Legal responsibility.
- Ethical responsibility.
- Charitable responsibility.

Figure 01: Carroll pyramid of corporate social responsibility

Source: (Sujin, 2019).

Social responsibility towards stakeholders:

Companies play an economic and social role and assume their responsibilities towards many parties, which take into account the working environment, which contains a large number of interest groups in activities that interact rapidly with general trends in the social environment.

Stakeholders:

Corporate social responsibility is an increasingly important building block in the academic environment, in addition to being an emphasis on the firm's practical agenda. Lee, Park, Rapert and Newman indicated that many companies set out corporate social responsibility procedures as an investment in the promotion of internal and external corporate values. Gossling and Vocht defines corporate social responsibility as the obligation of organizations to be responsible for their environment and stakeholders in a way that goes beyond financial aspects only (Albahussin, 2015, p 17). Stakeholders are many actors and parties, individuals, groups or other organizations.

The concept of social responsibility disclosure:

According to ISO 26000 on CSR, most companies must prepare annual reports on CSR activities. According to Mathews, there are three reasons for reporting CSR information: (1) to improve the financial and economic performance of a company, (2) to improve its legitimacy, and (3) to achieve social networking. A possible relationship may arise between corporate social responsibility disclosure and corporate performance when organizations are proactive in giving an impression of good faith by reproducing and disseminating knowledge of corporate social responsibility that meets or enhances stakeholder expectations (Siddiqui et al., 2023, p 01).

Social responsibility and its relationship to sustainable development:Definition of sustainable development:

The participation of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in sustainable development (SD) has become a common topic in research and business. However, joint research is still somewhat new and has not been fully studied. Corporate social responsibility is an effective strategy widely conceived as a corporate commitment or brand to maximize long-term economic, social and environmental well-being through business practices, policies and resources. Corporate social responsibility has shifted from charity to mandatory over decades, and has become a successful business model that provides comparative advantage in many respects and promotes corporate contributions to sustainable development. Corporate social responsibility has different definitions, but when it refers to sustainable development, the essence of corporate social responsibility is based on three dimensions: economic, social and environmental, which were only compatible with the triple bottom line of sustainable development. (Ye et al., 2020, p 01)

Sustainable development and its objectives:General concepts:

The term sustainable development is a modern term. The first emergence of this term was at the Club of Rome in 1986, which proposed the so-called Eco-development: the interaction between the economy and the environment between the North and the South. It concerns the future of man on this Earth. Before sustainable development is identified, the following terms must be known: Sustainability, a product of legal performance that reflects the ability of the company to maintain positively the company's activities affecting the economic, social and environmental system (Ivica, 2014, p. 15). 26),

Sustainable development goals and characteristics:

Sustainable development pursues a set of goals of economic prosperity based on ensuring a long-term competitive advantage, achieving social justice and improving the quality of life, as well as seeking cooperation and involvement between communities and companies in planning activities and taking advantage of all opportunities and strengths of society. Sustainable development also protects the natural and cultural environment by reducing pollution, reducing overuse of resources, preserving cultural heritage and biodiversity, and rational use of resources, reducing their depletion and rational use (Dumitu & Lulia, 2011). The Edward barbier study has identified several features of sustainable development. It is different from development. The former is considered to be more complex, especially in terms of nature and what is social in development, while sustainable development seeks to reduce and reduce global poverty.

Relationship between sustainable development and social responsibility as proposed by Brundland:

The dictionary of corporate social responsibility often refers to sustainable development. What echoes this idea when researchers try to define either concept, and the difference is whether corporate social responsibility and sustainable development have the same meaning, and if they are different, to what extent? For example, in defining sustainable development, Ebner and Baumgartner argue that the concept consists of economic, environmental and social issues at the corporate level, and that corporate social responsibility is the social thread for sustainable development that emphasizes the interests of stakeholders.

Similarly, many literatures agree that corporate social responsibility contributes to sustainable development, for example, in exploring the link between both concepts. Moon made it clear that the main driver of resource and capacity development in business organizations is the natural environment. By engaging in environmentally responsible activities, a business organization can have a more competitive advantage and/or become dominant than competitors who are not. In this regard, the link between the environment and the economy has been broken to ensure the sustainable development of the business organization.

Similarly, Ogini and Omojowo reveal that society and stakeholders are increasingly aware of social costs and business risks and that, therefore, many business organizations are reshaping their business models to become more socially responsible, which are more attractive to society and stakeholders. By doing so, they acquire a competitive advantage that prolongs their strength or sustainable development. (Xia et al., 2018, p 342).

The concept of social responsibility and sustainable development is closely linked. Socially committed companies take into account sustainable development in their three economic, social and environmental dimensions. The World Business Council for Sustainable Development considers corporate social responsibility as "the means by which companies fulfil their commitment to the issues raised by the issue of sustainable development."

Recommendations of the study:

Sustainable environmental development is a standard for socially responsible business organizations as one of the components of the new economy by improving the quality of life of the workforce, which is represented by stakeholders and society and seeks to improve the reputation of the organization and strengthen its long-term sustainability in the face of its competitors. The main findings can be highlighted in the following points:

- The social responsibility of business organizations is one of the fundamental pillars of sustainable environmental development.
- Voluntary commitment is one of the fundamental principles for fostering social responsibility in business organizations.

The exercise of corporate social responsibility contributes to social citizenship and changes the organization's perception of its objectives by paying attention to social aspects rather than seeking material economic gain.

Through its findings, we make the following recommendations:

Algerian business organizations must incorporate social responsibility programmes and activities into their strategies to improve their reputation and achieve sustainable development.

- Building on pioneering experiences in the area of social responsibility and environmental sustainability.
Promotion of scientific studies in the field of social responsibility through the exchange of international experiences.
- Encourage non-governmental bodies that disclose social responsibility practices in business organizations in the form of annual reports.
- Enact laws and legislation that require business organizations to be bound by environmental and community social responsibility.

CONCLUSION

Social responsibility is no longer limited to the sole objective of achieving the greatest return or profit, but its focus has been expanded by responding to the pressure of society and individuals in order to achieve the welfare of workers and improve their environmental conditions. It also covers all activities of a social nature undertaken by the institution, which are legally binding and which do not achieve economic benefit and which fall within the framework of the State ' s general social and economic development plan. Institutions have found themselves obliged to show accounting information in their financial reports on their contributions to social development.

Therefore, economic institutions have found themselves obliged to embody the principles and objectives of social responsibility by paying attention to stakeholders by providing low-cost, high-quality products and by working to preserve the environment with social objectives and profits that preserve their reputation and competitiveness.

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